

MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS AND EFFECTIVE SERVICE DELIVERY IN THE RIVERS STATE POLICE COMMAND, NIGERIA (2015–2023)

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Abstract

This study investigated the dynamics of employee innovation and service delivery in Rivers State Police Command between 2015 to 2023. The Nigerian Police annual report content was what motivated this study and it revealed how handicapped the Nigerian Police force have been, which was orchestrated by a combination of various factors that plagued the Nigerian Police Force. Among these factors were inadequate funding, high level of corruption, as well as poor conditions of service, among others. The Expectancy Theory propounded by Vroom in 1964 was adopted as the theoretical framework. While, method of research were both primary and secondary means of sourcing for data. The primary data sources were both questionnaire and interview. While, secondary data were sourced from textbooks, published articles, as well as internet materials, among others. However, a total number of 391 copies of questionnaire Samples were drawn for the study; whereas, interviews were conducted with senior police officers across the mine Area Police command in Rivers State. Findings showed that the welfare of personnel's of the Nigerian police force, Rivers State Police Command were not taken serious by the Nigerian government; their salaries have been very poor, their accommodation facilities were not for all, their police uniforms are hardly provided for them on time, among others. Therefore, the study recommends that the federal government should conduct a comprehensive review of Police Personnel's Salary Structure that will be commensurate with their service delivery in Rivers State.

Keywords: *Employee, Motivation, Service delivery, Security and Insecurity.*

Introduction

All formal organization in both public and private sector have certain goals set to achieve with the help of both man and material resources required. However, it is the human element that remains the major resource in all organizational settings because, it is the employees that make use of the material resources to actualise those sets of objectives. Be that as it may, the employee motivation stands as the driving force behind every human actions and remains a sin qua non to organizational success. Motivation is so important a factor because it enhances productivity and encourages individuals to give in their best performance in a bit to achieve organizational goals. Employee motivation is an internal act that propels individuals to engage in goal directed behaviour. It is often understood as a force that explains why people initiate, continue or terminate a certain behaviour at a particular point in time, (Agbenyegah, 2019). Employee motivation is therefore a key requirement for effective and efficient service delivery system for greater output or increased productivity in an organization.

Furthermore, service delivery system is another important part of an organization that enhances job performance. It does provide end-to-end lifestyle and can be used as a reference for running projects with similar features (Kumar, 2024). Camilleri, (2017) emphasises that one of the most important aspects of an

organization marketing strategy is the quality of services it provides. The quality of services rendered determines the organizational continued existence and their growth process, because doing so could assist them in addressing issues confronting them in a highly competitive market places.

Again, Hope, (2018) posit that service delivery refers to administrative and organizational aspects of improving the organizations commitment to providing programmes and services they offer to the people. The focus of service delivery is mapping out the expected output and contrasting it with the actual output generated by the service provider. That implies a comparison between enhancing the caliber of services provided and the expectations (Alix & Vallespir, 2013). The state being an invisible political entity through the existence of government, which discharges the responsibilities of the state through established institutions such as Ministries, Agencies and Departments, etc created for effective and efficient service delivery to the people.

Interestingly, the Nigerian Police Force is one of the institutions of the Nigerian State. The Nigerian Police Force is the principal law enforcement agency in the Nigerian State and was basically established to enforce the law and maintenance of order in the State. The operations of the Police Force help to curb challenges and escalating criminal issues, as well as offenses committed against one another as to achieve peaceful coexistence, tranquility and essentially provide security within the state (Murphy, 2009). Therefore, for the police to be effective and efficient in service delivery, they need to be motivated by means of adequate remuneration, promotion as at when due, proper training of police personnel, among other. Gjelsvik, (2020) emphasize on prioritization of motivation to enable Police officers render or discharge their duties which are based on Community, State and Federal policing with their ultimate interest as it concerns protection of life and property, maintenance of law and order detection of crime, preventing crime and curbing illegal activities (Harunavamwe & Kanengoni, 2013).

Also, insecurity across the Nigerian State have triggered a lot of concern, ranging from mass abductions at schools, kidnappings for ransom, armed conflicts between herdsmen and farmers, as well as Boko Haram and the Islamic States of West Africa Province (ISWAP) mutinies, etc. have aroused so much interest and curiosity on the roles of the police institution in the country. There has been a negative feelings and accusations that NPF personnels are not doing enough to combat the activities of these criminal elements and curb the rate of insecurity in different part of Nigeria (Akinyetun, 2022). These have been happening because the remuneration and welfare of the police are underfunded with poor salaries and poor welfare, coupled with lack of proper motivational reward systems that go a long way to affect service delivery system. Some factors have been identified to have hampered and mired NPF which include; inadequate funding, poor salaries, corruption, lack of training after training, outdated equipment that are not of modern technology, among others, which have been a huge challenge to NPF.

There is also the problem of discrimination against female police officers which has affected their level of motivation. Men often advance more rapidly in the Careers Compared to women. This exclusion limits their career progression and professional development. Again, female police officers often face systemic gender bias that limits their chances for promotion and causing gender imbalance. These have caused women to

often be overlooked for higher ranks despite meeting the same qualifications or having similar experience levels. It is against this backdrop that the study focuses on employee motivation and service delivery in Rivers State Police Command, 2015-2023. However, there are three objectives of this study which are to; examine the welfare packages at the disposal of Police Officers in Rivers State; analyse the factors that are responsible for poor motivation of Police Officers in Rivers State, and examine the negative impact of poor motivation of police officers in the fight against crime and criminality in Rivers State. These are supported by three research questions which include; what is the state of welfare; the factors responsible for poor motivation of police officers in Rivers State police command and the negative impact of poor motivation of police officers have caused in the fight against crime and criminality in Rivers State.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS:

Employee: whosoever that works for an established organization, institution, business settings, among others is an employee, so long as there is an exchange of money for the services rendered, as a compensatory aspect or form of payment known as a wage and salary. These are individuals that engage in a job on full-time or part-time basis; it can also be based on pensionary basis that they have some rights and retirement entitlement. Employees do have benefits to be compensated, trained and retraining, job security and career improvements that enhances their human development, (Aguinis & Bradley (2015); Dessler, (2020); Mathis, Jackson & Valentine, (2017) and Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart & Wright, (2019).

Motivation: Motivation is an incentive that entices and brings a yuphoric exitments that increases the drive to put in the very best of an employee, which enhances productivity and growth of an organization, enterprise or government administrative work, etc. Luthans and Stajkovic (1999) concluded that advancement of human resources through rewards, monetary incentives, and organizational behaviour modification has generated a large volume of debate in the human resource and sales performance field. Again, Orpen, (1997) emphasis much on the better relationship between mentors and mentees in the formal programme, the more mentees are motivated to work hard and be committed to their organization. For Kuo, (2013), a successful organization must combine the strengths and motivations of internal employees and respond to external changes and demands promptly to show the organisation's value. Panagiotakopoulos (2013) concluded that factors affecting staff motivation at a period where the financial rewards are kept to the least leads to stimulate employee performance. Thus, it is the responsibility of management personnel's to motivate their employees to work as per the expectation to enhance the organisation's performance.

Service Delivery: service delivery is a process, as well as an act of ensuring that services to humanity are rendered in the ways and manner it ought to be done. Whereas, the delivery aspect has to do with the conveyance means to ensure that the services get to the appropriate quarter as prescribed. Therefore, service delivery is a process and act of ensuring that services are conveyed to whosoever that needs or required the service at a particular given time and place. Faseluka (2010 cited in Afeez, 2020), goes to buttress the understanding of public service as the totality of the services directed to the management of human, material, and financial resources of the state for the provision of welfare services to the general

public. Further evidence can be drawn from the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). Specifically, section 169 of the Constitution makes provision for the existence of the Civil Service of the federation which states that “there shall be a civil service of the federation (CFRN, 1999-as amended). The provision further recognizes the civil service as the administrative machinery for implementing government policies and programmes with a view of advancing the welfare and wellbeing of the citizenry. Civil Service according to manual handbook in the Nigerian context also connotes an administrative machinery of the executive arms of the government that are responsible for policy implementations and execution for the service of the citizens. A civil servant in this regard represents an employee working and employed by civil service commission based on his expertise and professionalism. This is why Warren Fisher in his report of the Royal Commission of the Civil Service (1929) stated as follows “Ministers functions as policy determinant, and the moment policy is determined, civil servant has unquestionable responsibility of carrying out the policy in good faith without any fear or favour irrespective of whether he/she agrees with policy or not” (Warren, (1929) cited in Afeez, (2020).

Security and Insecurity: Security stands for protection of what needs to be protected. It can be viewed as an assured continuation of safety of life and property; which the absence of security becomes insecurity, which implies lack of protection, vulnerability and lack of safety, be it human or material things.

In the opinion of McGrew, (1988), “The Security of a nation hangs on two important pillars which are (1) the maintenance and protection of the socio-economic order in the case of internal and external threats and (2) the promotion of a preferred international order, which minimizes the threat to core values and interests, as well as domestic order” (1988 p.56).

Security is an all-encompassing condition which suggests that territory must be secured by a network of armed forces; that the sovereignty of the state must be guaranteed by a democratic and patriotic government, which in turn must be protected by the military police forces and the people themselves. The people must also be protected from devastating consequences of internal upheavals, such as unemployment, hunger, starvation, diseases, ignorance, homelessness, environmental degradation and pollution, as well as socio-economic injustices.

Dike, (2010) and Owede, (2011) extended the view expressed above by saying that, Nigeria’s Security should be based on a holistic view which sees the citizens as the primary beneficiaries of every security and developmental deliverable that the state can offer. In the view of Nwanegbo and Odigbo, (2013);

“Nigeria’s Security will include determinations to support the bulk of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. So, it can advance its interests and objectives to encompass internal and external aggression, control crime, eliminate corruption, enhance genuine development, progress and growth and improve the welfare and excellence of life of every citizen (2013 p.68).

According to the United Nations Development Programme (1994), human security could be defined as protection from hidden and hurtful disruptions in daily activities, at homes, offices or communities. That is, security is the state of being safe and secure from danger, it could also be protection from chronic threats such as hunger, disease – and repression. For the commission on Human Security (2003), human security is

the protection of important aspects of human lives in a way that would enhance human freedoms and fulfillment. Human Security encompasses freedom from want, harm, fear and the freedom to take appropriate actions without any form of hindrance. It is also the assurance of future well-being and freedom from threat.

On the contrary, the term insecurity has myriads of connotations. It could entail danger, hazard, uncertainty, and lack of protection or lack of safety (Ojeleye et al. 2022). Insecurity is the state of fear or anxiety stemming from concrete or alleged lack of protection. This refers to a lack of or inadequate freedom from danger. It implies that insecurity is an absence of peace, order, and security (Okonkwo, et al. 2015). Insecurity is the state of being prone or vulnerable to danger or threat of danger. In this scenario, the tendency to experience hurt based on insufficient measures against danger is very bright. The danger in this context is the condition of being susceptible to harm or injury. Again, insecurity is the state of being exposed to risk or anxiety.

Furthermore, according to Beland, (2005), insecurity entails the “Absence of Safety from crime (being unsafe) and lack of freedom from psychological harm (unprotected) from emotional stress resulting from a paucity of assurance that an individual is accepted, has opportunity and choices to fulfil his or her own potential including freedom from fear (2005 p.112).

Also, Achinuba and Ighomereho, (2013) put it differently, to them insecurity affects the ignorant and weak people mostly, as they put it;

“Those effected by insecurity are not only unclear or ignorant of what would transpire but, they are also not able to stop it or defend themselves when it occurs” (2013 p.113).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK:

The Theory adopted to stand as the theoretical framework for this study is the expectancy theory. The expectancy theory was propounded by Vroom in 1964, which suggests that individuals are motivated to perform, if they know that their extra input and output performance is recognized and rewarded (Vroom, 1964). Consequently, organisations and institutions using performance-based pay can expect improvements, because performance-based pay can link rewards to the amount of products employees produce. According to Cameron, et al. (2001), the validity of the theory is predicated on the doctrine that rewards lead to improved performance. The theory is predicated on the following assumptions as gleaned from Ngatia, (2017), they are; Rational Decision-making by individuals who calculate the expectant success, as well as the role of rewards prior to making or taking a decision, with adequate considerations by weighing the potentialities; Individual Differences are Considered with regards to motivation, hence, preferential rewards are given accordingly; Behaviour is Goal-Oriented because individual are motivated by goals and objectives as the case may be; People are motivated by outcomes hence, their actions are driven based on what will be the out come; Lastly, is Perceived Relationships among effort, performance and reward because people are often motivated when they clearly understand the connection between their effort and the reward that follows. In this regard, Ngatia, (2017) applied this theory in the course of analyzing the effects of non-monetary rewards on service provision, and they found that it was significant.

This theory is adequate for this study because, there is a nexus between motivational rewards and high performance in police force service delivery system in Nigeria.

METHOD OF RESEARCH:

Given the nature of the research, the study adopted the descriptive and survey research designs. The designs were arranged in the following ways; data were sourced from both primary and secondary sources. Primary sources of data were gathered from copies of questionnaires and interviews. While, that of secondary sources came from textbooks, journal articles, as well as institutional publications, among others.

The population of the study was the Rivers State Police Command that is made up of 9 Area Commands, with 52 Divisional Police Headquarters, 25 Police Stations and 23 Police outposts. It is headed by a Commissioner of Police and has Staff strength of about 17, 207 police officers (Wikipedia, 2025).

The study equally adopted the purposive and quota techniques. In the purposive sampling techniques, the selected respondents are seen to be knowledgeable enough to give account of the subject matter under investigation.

Lastly, the method of analysis was the simple percentage method of analysis.

THE COLONIAL ORIGINS OF THE NIGERIAN POLICE:

To understand how the structure of the Nigerian Police functions. It is necessary to examine how the structure came to be. It is, therefore, imperative to consider the origins of the Nigerian police. However, the information on the origins of the Nigerian Police is sketchy. The official national webpage on the history of the Nigerian Police gives the following summary:

In 1879, a 1200-member armed paramilitary Hausa Constabulary was formed. In 1896, the Lagos Police was established. A similar Force, the Niger Coast Constabulary was formed in Calabar in 1894 under the newly proclaimed Niger Coast Protectorate. In the north, the Royal Niger Company set up the Royal Niger Company Constabulary in 1888. When the protectorate of Northern and Southern Nigeria were proclaimed in the early 1900s, part of the Royal Niger Company Constabulary became the Northern Nigeria Police and part of the Niger Coast Constabulary became the Southern Nigeria Police. During the colonial period, most police were associated with local governments (native authorities). In the 1960s, under the First Republic, these forces were first regionalized and then nationalized. The British merged the Lagos colony and the southern and northern protectorates in 1913 and named the new colony Nigeria. The northern and southern regional police forces were later merged, in 1930, to form the colony's first national police – the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) (Wikipedia, 2013 p.1).

Hence, it is certain that the police force/service was set up within the colonial setting. There were components of law and order before colonisation, but the trappings of these were overpowered by the colonial experience and supplanted by the coloniser's framework of law and order. And in this regard, there has been a part composed of Anglophone law and order in colonial Africa. And it is to these compositions we turn for an understanding of the roots of the Nigerian police as a complicit portion of the colonial experience.

In 1910, 27% of the expenditure of the colony called Northern Nigeria was devoted to protecting the colony from internal dissent. So, we resisted the colonialist's power, and it turned out that the colonialist's power was the colonialist's power. Consequently, the “Egba rising of 1918 was suppressed at the cost of several hundred lives, and the ‘Women’s War’ culminated in the army firing on crowds of protesting women at Aba in 1929” (Killingray, 1986, p.420).

As a result of the growing need to suppress dissent, after independence, law and order institutions were far more developed than any other. There are some schools, some hospitals and some means of transport but public order agencies predominate. After independence, the Africanisation of the police resulted in only superficial changes. The Nigerian police have been instilled with a culture of brutality, exploitation, repression and oppression. It seems that the only way to maintain the stability of a country with an uncertain constitution is through the constant and persistent display of force. A crime is only a crime when it involves resistance to the force of the state (Ayoade, 2011). This is contrary to the function and culture of the police in the mother/colony country. For example, in the UK it has always been understood that the police are primarily responsible for the maintenance of public order and, the prevention and detection of crimes in the state. It also protects the life, liberty and property of the people.

COMMUNITY POLICING PROGRAMMES IN NIGERIA:

Community policing programs in Nigeria have emerged as a significant strategy to address the widespread issue of insecurity and crime in the country. These programs aim to establish closer collaboration and partnership between law enforcement agencies and local communities, empowering citizens to actively participate in crime prevention and reduction efforts. This article explores the concept of community policing in Nigeria, its objectives, and key features, and evaluates the effectiveness of these programs. It includes examples of successful community policing initiatives implemented in Nigeria and provides references for further reading.

Community policing in Nigeria is based on the principle that law enforcement agencies and the community should work together to identify and address the root causes of criminal activities, maintain law and order, and enhance public safety. The primary goal of community policing programs is to foster trust, build positive relationships, and increase mutual understanding between the police and the community. By empowering communities and involving citizens in crime prevention, these initiatives aim to create safer and more secure neighbourhoods.

Key features of community policing programs in Nigeria include partnership, problemsolving, information, and community engagement:

Partnership: Community policing programs emphasize collaboration and partnerships between law enforcement agencies, community leaders, residents, and other stakeholders. This multi-sectoral approach ensures that community needs and concerns are addressed effectively. **Problem-Solving:** Community policing shifts the focus from reactive policing to proactive problem-solving. Law enforcement officers work closely with the community to identify and address the underlying causes of crime through targeted

interventions and strategies. **Information Sharing:** Open communication and information sharing between the police and the community are essential in community policing. Establishing trust and effective two-way communication channels enable the timely exchange of information, leading to improved crime prevention and response.

Community Engagement: Creating avenues for community participation and engagement is a fundamental aspect of community policing. Programmes may involve community forums, neighbourhood watch groups, youth outreach initiatives, and partnership-building activities to empower and mobilise the community.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE:

Several empirical studies highlight how bribery and corruption within the NPF undermine its effectiveness. Uzor et al (2024) conducted a study titled Effect of Motivation on Job Satisfaction and Performance: A Study of Nigeria Police Force, examined the effect of motivation strategies on job satisfaction and performance. Data were elicited using questionnaire. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. The responses were analysed using both simple and multiple linear regressions. Findings revealed that the promotion strategy has a significant impact on motivation and performance, while the other two variables (police training and retraining strategy, and donation of operational vehicles) do not show a statistically significant relationship at the conventional alpha level of 0.05. Overall, the findings indicate that the promotion strategy has a stronger influence on job satisfaction and performance in the Nigeria Police Force compared to the other strategies (training and re-training and donation of operational vehicle) examined. The study recommends that the management of NPF should consider ways to make the promotion process transparent, fair, and rewarding for deserving officers.

Onuoha (2025) conducted a study titled Assessment of Adequacy of Equipment, Motivation and Incentives of the Nigerian Police force: Implications for Effective Policing in Nigeria, assessed the adequacy of equipment, motivation and incentives of the Nigerian police force and its implications for effective policing in Nigeria. Over time, successive governments have not paid maximum premium towards enhancing effective policing in Nigeria.

Technological equipment was found to be pivotal in enhancing police effectiveness but such technological equipment was not seen to be adequate thereby limiting the effective operation of the police. Pay rise, good working environment, hygiene, recognition, rewards, promotion and some other indicators were identified as motivational and incentive drives that can boost the morale and productivity of the Police personnel but were not sufficient. The study concluded that the problem of Nigerian police is not with the personnel but as a result inadequate equipment and inappropriate motivation. The study recommended that the police force should be provided with proper equipment and adequate incentives to bring out the best in the personnel

A study by Alemika and Chukwuma aimed at studying the poor performances of Nigerian police force (2000) found that corruption in the NPF is systemic, leading to diminished trust between the Police and the public. Studies indicate that the Nigerian Police Force is often criticized for its lack of professionalism,

especially in their engagement with civilians. For instance, Okafor (2007) examined the recurring incidences of human rights abuses within the Nigerian Police Force. He highlighted cases of Police brutality and extrajudicial killings which have led to public outcry against the Nigerian Police Force. He recommended the reform of the Nigerian Police Force to enable the institution to discharge its function effectively.

A study carried out by Aborisade (2018), noted that a large section of the public fears the Police, perceiving them as a threat rather than protectors. This perception impedes community Policing efforts and cooperation in criminal investigations. Studies carried out by

Epilogue et al. (2014) revealed poor response times and weak investigative capacities of the Nigerian Police Force. Their findings revealed that lack of modern equipment and inadequate training hampers the Nigerian Police Force's ability to combat crime effectively. Their study recommends the proper funding of the Nigerian Police Force through an increment in budgetary allocation to enable the Police to live up to its responsibility of protecting lives and properties.

Adebayo (2013) study focuses on the Nigerian Police Force as a highly centralized entity which has impacted negatively on the capability of the NPF to effectively combat crime. The study finds that the federal control of the NPF limits community-based approaches and quick responses to local crime. The study recommends the decentralization of the NPF to enable state governments to establish a Policing system that suits their local peculiarity. Agbiboa (2015) study focuses on Boko Haram insurgency, kidnappings, banditry, and communal clashes in parts of Nigeria. The study demonstrates the Nigerian Police's ineffectiveness in managing severe security threats to the low morale that bedevil the NPF.

An empirical study by Rotimi (2019) focused on the failure of oversight institutions to check Nigerian Police excesses. The study focuses on the role of oversight bodies like the Police Service Commission (PSC) and their inability to hold the NPF accountable. Similarly, Adebayo (2013) looked at the history of Nigerian Police reforms and concluded that many reforms have failed to achieve their objectives due to lack of political will, corruption, and inadequate funding. A study carried out by the CLEEN Foundation (2008) showed that there is a serious gap in capacity building within the NPF. The study finds out that Nigerian Police Officers often lack adequate training in modern crime-fighting techniques and human rights standards. The study recommends proper funding for the Nigerian Police Force.

Reports by organisations such as Amnesty International have documented numerous cases of Nigerian Police extrajudicial killings, torture, and illegal detentions. Scholars such as Okafor (2007) have explored these abuses from empirical standpoints, showing how they undermine public confidence in the Police. The #EndSARS protests in 2020 have been a recent focus in empirical work, where the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) was accused of widespread abuses. Anayo (2021) explored the state's heavy-handed response to these protests, highlighting the NPF's strained relationship with the youth and broader civil society. Similarly, Daramola (2021) explored the recent Police reform initiatives, especially following the #EndSARS protests, focusing on whether there has been any significant improvement in Nigerian Police behaviour or service delivery.

From the review of empirical studies, it revealed that a lot of studies have been carried out on motivation and service delivery. For instance, by Alemika and Chukwuma (2000) found that corruption in the NPF is systemic, leading to diminished trust between the Police and the public. Okafor (2007) examined the recurring incidences of human rights abuses within the Nigerian Police Force. Similarly, Rotimi (2019) focused on the failure of oversight institutions to check Nigerian Police excesses. This study re-affirmed with concrete evidence that poor remuneration or general work conditions of police officers account for the Nigerian police inability to truly render desired service to the public. This is the gap this present study filled

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS:

Simple percentage method was used to analyse the data obtained from field, which were then displayed in tables.

This section presents answers to the research questions; it also presents the discussion of the findings which are based on the research questions

Table 1: Nigeria Police Force Rivers state Police Command is poorly funded?

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	309	86.5%
No	45	12.6%
Unknown	3	0.8%
Total	357	100%

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

As can be seen from the above table, three hundred and nine (309) respondents, or 86.5% of the sample, averred that the Nigerian Police Force Rivers state Police Command is poorly funded. In contrast, forty-five (45) respondents, or 12.6% of the sample, said no to the question. In a similar vein, three (3) respondents, or 0.8% of the sample, answered "I don't know" to the question.

Table 2: Personnel of the Nigerian Police Force, Rivers State Police Command is not well remunerated?

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	218	61.1%
No	133	37.2%
Unknown	6	1.6%
Total	357	100%

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

From the above table, two hundred and eighteen (218) respondents which represent 61.1% are of the view that personnel of the Nigerian Police Force, Rivers State Police Command are not well remunerated while one hundred and thirty-three (133) respondents which represent 37.2% are of the view that personnel of

the Nigerian Police Force, Rivers State Police Command are well remunerated. Similarly, six (6) respondents which represent 1.6% said “they don’t know” in response to the question.

Table 3: The Nigerian Police Force Rivers state Police Command does not provide adequate training for it personnel?

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	217	60.7%
No	131	36.6%
Unknown	9	2.5%
Total	357	100%

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

According to the aforementioned table, 217 respondents, or 60.7% of the sample, believe that the Nigerian Police Force Rivers state Police Command does not provide adequate training for it personnel. However, 131 respondents, or 36.6% of the sample, disagree, stating that the Nigerian Police Force Rivers state Police Command provide adequate training for it personnel. In a similar vein, nine (9) respondents, or 2.5% of the sample, answered "I don't know" to the question.

Table 4: Can we attribute low wage of Police Officers as one of the factors that affect the motivation of Police personnel, Rivers State command?

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	259	72.5%
No	85	23.8%
Unknown	13	3.6%
Total	357	100%

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

From the above table, two hundred and fifty-nine (259) respondents which represent 72.5 % are of the view that low wage of Police Officers is one of the factors that affect the motivation level of Police personnel in Rivers State while eighty-five (85) respondents which represent 23.8% disagreed to the question. Similarly, thirteen (13) respondents which represent 3.6% said "I don't know" to the question.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS:

Based on the data presented, the following findings are reached

1. The study found that the welfare of personnel of Nigerian Police force Rivers State is not taking serious by the Nigerian government. Salaries of personnel are very poor, accommodation is not being provided for personnel and this among other has affected the morale of personnel in the discharge of their duties. These assertions correspond with responses from respondents from field work. For instance, in table 4.2.1 were 309 respondents, or 86.5% of the sample, averred that the Nigeria Police Force Rivers state Police Command is poorly funded. In contrast, 45 respondents, or 12.6% of the sample, said no to the

question. In a similar vein, three (3) respondents, or 0.8% of the sample, answered "I don't know" to the question

2. The study also found that corruption and poor wage among others are some of the factors that affect the motivation of Police personnel in Nigeria and Rivers state command in particular. Corruption by senior Police officers and Nigerian government has affected the capacity of Officers to discharge their duties effectively. These assertions correspond with responses from respondents from field work. For instance, in table 4.2.4 were two hundred and fifty nine (259) respondents which represent 72.5 % are of the view that low wage of Police officers is one of the factors that affect the motivation level of Police personnel in Rivers State while eighty-five (85) respondents which represent 23.8% disagreed to the question. Similarly, thirteen (13) respondents which represent 3.6% said "I don't know" to the question.

3. The work found that the low motivation of Police personnel in Nigeria has led to increase wave of cultism in Rivers State. This assertion corresponds with responses from respondents from field work. For instance, in table 4.2.7 were two hundred and two (202) respondents which represent 56.5% are of the opinion that the low motivation of Police personnel in Nigeria has led to increase wave of cultism in Rivers State while one hundred and forty-five (145) respondents which represent 40.6% disagreed that to the question. Similarly, ten (10) respondents which represent 2.8% said they do not know.

4. The work also found that Rivers State government has provided operational vehicles to personnel of Rivers state Police command to aid their operation. This assertion corresponds with responses from respondents from field work. For instance, in table 4.2.10 were two hundred and seventy-eight (278) respondents which represent 77.8% hold the view that Rivers state government has provided operational vehicles to personnel of Rivers state Police command to aid their operation in the state while fifty-seven (57) respondents which represent 15.9% disagreed to the question. Similarly, twenty-two (22) respondents which represent 6.1% said they do not know.

CONCLUSION:

Motivation is a critical factor in the effective service delivery of any organisation, including the Nigeria Police force. According to Adebayo and Kolawole (2016), motivation is a psychological process that causes the arousal, direction, and persistence of voluntary actions that are goal-directed. In the context of the Nigeria Police force, motivation can be seen as a tool that influences the behaviour of Police officers towards achieving the organisational goals of maintaining law and order. Motivation whether intrinsic or extrinsic, can significantly impact the performance and productivity of police officers. The role of motivation in the Nigeria Police Force has been extensively studied.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. The federal government should conduct a comprehensive review of Police salary structures to ensure they are commensurate with the risks and responsibilities of the job.

2. The federal government should establish an independent internal anti-corruption unit within the Nigerian Police Force with the authority to investigate and sanction corrupt senior Police officers and their likes.
3. The federal government should provide better remuneration, healthcare, housing, and insurance packages for Police personnel to boost their morale and encourage greater commitment to duty.
4. The federal government should complement the provision of vehicles with other essential logistics such as fuel supply, communication equipment, GPS systems, and spare parts to ensure effective deployment.

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